

Developing speaking skills of intermediate learners through discussion based activities.

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Annotation: In this article, it is known about how to develop speaking skill for foreign language learners besides this, students can introduce a various ways if they want to speak fluently.

Key words: fluency, pronunciation, accuracy and conversation skills, transmission, storytelling techniques, encoded for transmission.

Speaking is one of the four macro skills to be developed as a means of effective communication in both first and second language learning contexts. In the English as a Foreign Language (EFL) pedagogy environment, how to increase speaking competence and confidence for undergraduate students tends to be a crucial question among instructors. This concern led to a qualitative research design as an action study in a regular course employing a task-based approach. The findings indicated that confidence, creativity of topics, and speaking competence were the key aspects of improvement when speaking to the audience.

Speaking where the comprehension of what has been said is necessary for what each participant says next. Both kinds of language skills, receptive and productive, need to be practiced by students in teaching-learning ESL. Receptive skills are the ways in which people extract meaning from the discourse they hear and see. Besides listening, reading is included in receptive skills. While productive skills are the skills that involve the process of language production either in oral or written forms (Harmer, 2001:246). Speaking is one of the productive skills that must be mastered by students in order that they can carry out a conversation with other people with

ease. Chaney and Burke (1998:3) have said that “the model of the communication system for interpersonal communication is through speech”. In this model, an information source emits a message, which is encoded for transmission as a signal. This signal passes through a channel to a receiver, which decodes the message for use at its destination.

Initially, Through storytelling techniques, individuals can learn to express themselves and make sense of the external world.

Furthermore, in 1992, the North Dakota Center for the book also began to promote storytelling and festivals (or “tellebrations”). They have stated that: Storytelling to Improve Speaking Skills. Storytelling is an art form through which we have preserved our heritage, passed on traditions, learned skills, and most importantly, developed our limitless imaginations. Storytelling is at the heart of human experience; a means by which we gain a better understanding of ourselves and our world (Storytelling On-line). (North Dakota Center, 1992:212)

The statement above shows that with storytelling we can use our imaginations to develop our background knowledge. The use of storytelling to communicate ideas and to express one’s experiences is obvious. Stories are frequently passed between people. And also, storytelling is a good means of developing speaking skills. According to Iverson and Lancey (1961:130), engaging students in storytelling activities develops communication skills and encourages shared learning experiences. Storytelling is a universal function of language and one of the main ingredients of casual conversation. Using storytelling, students can practice listening and speaking skills in a fun and interactive way.

When the teacher tells stories to the students, she communicates with them, entertains them, and passes on information. Besides that, many students still have problems when they have to speak in front of the class, getting confused and losing

the theme, even losing their train of thought so that their speaking becomes unclear, so one way of overcoming these problem is by using storytelling which has been proved is an effective way of improving the speaking skills of students.

Telling stories is a good way to combine instruction and entertainment. Stories are an effective tool for teaching languages (Malkina, 1995:1, as cited in Fitria, 2000). Children usually love stories. While listening to stories, children develop a sense of structure that will later help them to understand the more complex stories of literature. Through storytelling the teacher can create an atmosphere in which the students can learn English whilst being entertained. Procedures of Teaching Speaking with Storytelling Techniques. There are some procedures that can be followed by teachers in applying storytelling in teaching speaking. They are as the following

Oral language is one of the most important skills your students can master—both for social and academic success. Learners use this skill throughout the day to process and deliver instructions, make requests, ask questions, receive new information, and interact with peers.

Encourage conversation.

Every social interaction gives students a new opportunity to practice language. Some of your students might need a little guidance from you to engage in conversations, so spark interactions whenever you can. Ask questions, rephrase the student's answers, and give prompts that encourage oral conversations to continue. It is given useful ways for conversation.

Model syntactic structure.

Your students may not use complete oral syntax in informal speech, but encourage them to do so when they're in the classroom. When a student uses fragmented syntax, model complete syntax back to them. This builds oral language

skills *and* gives students practice in a skill necessary for mastering written language.

Maintain eye contact.

Engage in eye contact with students during instruction and encourage them to do the same. Maintaining eye contact will help learners gauge their audience’s attention and adjust their language, their volume, or the organization of their speech. This will help them be better understood, communicate more clearly, and successfully interpret nonverbal cues about their clarity.

Remind students to speak loudly and articulate clearly.

Ask students to feel the muscles used for speech while they’re talking and monitor their volume and articulation. Remind them that clear and loud-enough speech is essential for holding the attention of the group and communicating their information and opinions effectively.

Have students summarize heard information.

Encourage students to verbally summarize or otherwise discuss the information they hear. This should begin in kindergarten and continue with increasingly difficult questions as students grow older. Teach students to ask for clarification when they don’t understand something, and emphasize that they can ask you directly or query fellow students.

Model and guide sentence construction.

Some students have trouble getting started with the wording of a sentence. Saying the beginning word or phrase for the student can help the student structure their response. Give students time for thinking and formulating an oral or written response. Students’ explicit experience in both producing their own oral language and processing others’ language will help facilitate their comprehension of reading material.

Explain the subtleties of tone.

Your students have probably experienced playground arguments related to tone; misunderstandings are common when students are using loud outdoor voices. Remind your students how tone of voice—which includes pitch, volume, speed, and rhythm—can change the meaning of what a speaker says. Often, it’s not what they say, it’s how they say it that can lead to misunderstanding of motives and attitudes. Ask your students to be mindful of tone when they’re trying to get a message across, and adjust their volume and pitch accordingly.

Attend to listening skills.

Ensure that your students are listening by using consistent cues to get their attention. You might use a phrase like “It’s listening time” to give students a reminder. Some students might also benefit from written reminders posted prominently on your wall.

Incorporate a “question of the day.”

During each school day’s opening activities, ask a question to encourage talk. (You can even write one on the board so your students can read it and start thinking about their answer as soon as they come in.) Start with simple one-part questions like “What is your favorite animal?” If a student doesn’t answer in a complete sentence, model a complete sentence and ask the student to repeat your model. Once your students are successfully answering these simple questions in complete sentences, move to two-part questions that require more complex answers: “What is your favorite animal? Why?”

Compile a class booklet of students’ phrases.

Give your students a sentence to finish, such as “When my dog got lost I looked...” Have each student contribute a prepositional phrase to complete the sentence (e.g., *at the grocery store, in the park, under the bed*). Then have your students create a class booklet by writing and illustrating their phrases. When all the phrase pages are assembled into a booklet, students can practice reading the very long

sentence with all the places they looked for the dog. Encourage them to come up with a conclusion to the story.

Teach concept words.

Some students may have difficulty with abstract concepts such as *before*, *after*, or *following*, and with sequences such as days of the week or months of the year. To help students learn and retain these concepts, you may need to present and review them many times and in multiple ways. For example:

- You might ask students to identify which holiday comes in each month and then review holidays for other months in sequence: “Groundhog Day is in February. What holiday is in March? In April?”
- Have students identify the month before or after a given month. “May is before June and after April.” “May is between April and June.”

Nowadays, it is burning problem to improve speaking skill among the students. The most scientists gave many methods of speaking however, they may be difficult for some students. Here are four tips to improve your fluency, pronunciation, accuracy and conversation skills.

If you're looking for ways to improve your spoken communication in English, you're not alone. How can I improve my English speaking skills?' is one of the most popular questions we get asked. So here's what everyone wants to know. Read on for four tips to improve your fluency, pronunciation, accuracy and conversation skills in English.

Speak English to practise and improve

Speaking a language is a skill, like driving a car, playing a musical instrument or learning to swim. To be a good driver, you need to practise driving. You can read a book about car mechanics. You can study the rules of the road. Nothing is as good

Another thing is pronunciation, or just feeling the words in your mouth. Speaking a foreign language is a physical workout for your mouth, and you want to get in the gym! You're also practising fluency. Next time you have to talk about that same topic, the ideas and words will flow more easily. By training yourself to notice and correct mistakes, you'll improve your accuracy too.

Work on your listening skills

Watching series and films in English, or listening to audio designed for your level, is great for your pronunciation and intonation. Listening to English is also a good way to notice how grammar is used or to pick up new words and phrases. But not only all of that! Here's the big one.

Being a good listener is a *really* important part of a good conversation. We often forget this when we're concentrating on what we're going to say. You don't even need to be that good at speaking English. If you can listen, understand and show interest, people will absolutely love talking to you. And that means more English speaking practice, more opportunities to improve your speaking and more of that lovely, warm feeling that happens when you use your English to connect with someone.

Enjoy improving your spoken communication in English! Choose one tip from this article and start improving your English speaking skills right away.

In conclusion, being a good speaker is a really significant part of a good orally speech. These methods of improving speaking skill can help to increase and achieve our goals in our career which are mentioned before.

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